

Preparation and characterization of the radiation crosslinked shape memory EVA/HDPE

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Background

SMPs have the advantages such as good shape recoverability, simple preparation process, low cost and good processability. SMPs have widespread application in heat shrinkable tube, space-deployable structure, smart textile and biomedical materials, etc.

Radiation crosslinking, which has the advantages of controllable crosslinking degree, uniformity and pure system, is one of the effective methods to obtain good space environment adaptability.

Heat shrinkable tube

Deployable architecture

Biodegradable suture for wound closure

Outline

- 01 ▶ Preparation of radiation crosslinked SMP**
 - Preparation process
 - Tensile test
- 02 ▶ Properties Characterization of the Radiation Crosslinked SMP**
 - Shape memory behavior
 - Environmental adaptability

Preparation of SMP--EVA/HDPE

Table 1 experiment conditions for samples.

Samples	[HDPE]/M%	[EVA]/M%	Time/min	[Radiation dose]/kGy	Temperature/°C
A	40	60	20	0~320	150
B	50	50	20	0~320	150
C	60	40	20	0~320	150
D	70	30	20	0~320	150
E	80	20	20	0~320	150

In this paper, high density polyethylene (HDPE) and ethylene-vinyl acetate (EVA) were used as the raw material to prepare the new radiation crosslinked EVA/HDPE SMPs. The EVA/HDPE blends with different mass ratios were mixed in an open mill for 20min, with approximately the same mixing temperature of 150°C. The prepared blanks were shaped into plate specimens by hot pressing by a vulcanizer, with approximately the same pressure of 10 MPa. Then the plate specimens were crosslinked by 1 MeV electron beam.

Preparation of SMP--Tension test (without crosslinking)

Fig.1. The tensile property of samples with various mass fractions: (a), (b), (c).

Fig.1 (a) and (b) shows the tensile break extension percentage and strength without radiation, we can see that flake samples have better tensile properties when mass ratio of EVA less than 30%. Fig.1 (c) shows that the tensile break extension percentage of samples with 30% EVA are less than both of pure EVA and HDPE. This result shows that EVA and HDPE are incompletely compatible, we have to choose one as main component to improve the compatibility. In this research we choose 30% EVA, because the tensile properties of this mass ratio are enough.

Preparation of SMP—Tension test (crosslinked)

Fig.2 is the tension test result of 30% EVA flake samples with different radiation dose. we can see that the tensile properties significantly increased after radiation. And the maximum tensile properties was on the radiation dose of 150-200kGy. Based on the above results, we choose 30% EVA in mass ratio and 160kGy radiation dose as main process parameters.

Fig.2. The tensile property of samples with various radiation dose.

Shape memory behavior--Expansion deformation

Fig.3. Shape memory properties test.

Fig.4. Shape recovery of tensile deformation

Table 2 Shape memory properties test result

Dose/kGy	EVA/%	Deformation/%	Rf /%	Rr /%
160	30	200	95	96

Fig.3 displays shape memory behavior test process. First, we heated samples to 140°C and kept temperature for 5mins. Then, we tensed the samples to 200% and cooled these sample by water. And then, measured shape memory fixed ratio. Finally, reheated the samples to 140°C and kept temperature until recovery process completed, measured the shape memory recovery ratio the same time. Table.2 shows a good shape memory behavior test results, the shape memory fixed ratio is 95%, and the shape memory recovery ratio is 96%.

Shape memory behavior--Bending deformation

Fig.6. Shape memory properties test.

Fig.6 displays bending elastic recovery test process. First, we heated samples to 140°C and kept temperature for 5mins. Then, we bended the samples to 180° and cooled these sample by water. And then, measured shape memory fixed ratio. Finally, reheated the samples to 140°C and kept temperature until recovery process completed, measured the shape memory recovery ratio the same time.

Fig.7. shows the process of shape recovery of bending deformation. The shape memory fixed ratio is 100%, and the shape memory recovery ratio is 94%.

Fig.7. Shape recovery of bending deformation.

Environmental adaptability-- Vacuum gassing

Vacuum gas test temperature is 125°C, the holding time is 24 hours, the main measurement and calculation of TML (total mass loss) and CVCM (condensable volatile content of the materials) two important parameters. We can calculate TML and CVCM by referring to the Ministry of Aerospace Industry QJ1558-88 "vacuum material volatilization test method. Table.3 shows the excellent vacuum gassing performance of samples, TML and CVCM are both far less than ECSS-Q-ST-70-02 standard.

Table 3 Vacuum gassing test result

Name	TML指标	CVCM指标
Test result	TML=0.22%	CVCM=0.02%
ECSS-Q-ST-70-02	TML≤1.00%	CVCM≤0.10%

Environmental adaptability--Thermal Properties

Fig.8. Thermal Properties test:(a) DSC, (b) TG

The result of DSC (differential scanning calorimetry) analysis showed that the crystal phase is almost complete melting at 140°C. TG(The thermogravimetric) analysis showed that the prepared EVA / HDPE shape memory polymer did not undergo thermal decomposition at 300 °C.

Summary

- To obtain EVA/HDPE blends with good shape memory characteristics and mechanical properties, the content of EVA should be less than 30%, electron irradiation dose should be in the range from 150kGy to 200kGy.
- The EVA/HDPE blends prepared with 3:7 ratio and 160kGy irradiation dose shows good shape memory properties. When the tensile deformation reached 200%, the shape fixed rate was 95% and the recovery rate was 96%. As bending deformation was 180°, the shape fixed rate is 100% and the recovery rate is 95.5%.
- The EVA/HDPE blends prepared with 3:7 ratio and 160kGy irradiation dose shows excellent gassing performance, the total mass loss rate and the condensable volatile content of the materials was 0.22% and 0.02%, respectively.

Thanks for your attention !

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